

MANNERISM IN ITALIAN ART IN XVI-XVII CENTURIES

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Abstract

In XVI century, Mannerism replaced the masterpieces of the Renaissance and there was a transition from the High Renaissance to the Baroque style. The term "manierismo" is an Italian word meaning "manner, style". It is possible to identify two main stages in the Mannerism revolution. The first stage covers the 20s and 30s of XVI century. At this stage, Mannerism is considered as a trend directed against the previous trends. The second stage of Mannerism coincides with the stabilization of the Italian feudal-Catholic movement. It began in the 1540s and lasted until the beginning of XVII century. During this time, Mannerism already went beyond the boundaries of its previous circle, became the dominant trend in palatial art and the entire territory of the country. Y.K.Pantormo, R.Fiorentino, S.Pyombo, P.Vaga, C.Romano, Parmigianino, A.Bronzino, F.Salviati, N.Abbate, F.Barocci, El Greco and others can be mentioned as representatives of the mannerism trend in painting.

Keywords: Mannerism, Italian Renaissance, epigone, Pantormo, Parmigianino, Bronzino, El Greco, fresco, Palacio del Te

Art never stays the same because it is closely related to changes in society. In the XVI century, Mannerism replaced the masterpieces of the Renaissance and there was a transition from the High Renaissance to the Baroque style. The term "manierismo" is an Italian word meaning "manner, style". "The term Mannerism was used in the sixteenth century to denote a social movement, to convey an elegant virtuoso quality, or to describe a particular technique. But later, for example, in the seventeenth century, Giovanni Pietro Bellori used the word "la maniera" to refer to post-Raphaelite art, especially from the 1530s to the 1540s. Since XIX century, the term has been used to denote post-Renaissance and pre-Baroque art" [8].

The trend was popular from about the 1920s to the 1590s. At the beginning of XVII century, it became completely baroque. "The invasion and looting of Italy by the Spanish army opened a new stage full of decline in the country's destiny" [6, p. 253]. The social and political crisis that engulfed Italy in the 20s and 30s of XVI century determined a sharp turn in the fate of the Italian Renaissance. It was characterized by sharp contradictions. Mannerism was full of contradictions characteristic of that period of crisis.

Commenting on the last stage of the renaissance, S. Aliyeva notes that humanist culture experienced a deep crisis in this period, and anti-Renaissance and anti-classical trends were manifested in the mannerism trend [1, p. 275].

The humanist principles of the Renaissance could no longer cover the spiritual life of all Italy. In the 1520s, the trend of Mannerism began to form under these conditions in the centers where the Renaissance experienced a crisis. Historians of XVII century, who began to use the concept of mannerism often, attributed it to the work of the epigones of Raphael and Michelangelo. In XX century, this concept was interpreted in different ways [5, p. 218]. According to Fakhreddin Gechen, the main features of Mannerism were the neutrality of space, neglect of nature, "S"-shaped figures and their stretching and emphasizing, violation of proportionality and symmetry [2, p. 378].

Art critic I.A. Smirnova determines that there are two main stages in the Mannerism revolution [5, p. 219]. One can agree with him by considering the general picture of Mannerism. The first stage covers the 20s and 30s of XVI century. At this stage, Mannerism is considered as a trend directed against the previous trends. In cities like Florence, Rome, Parma, which were covered by economic and political crisis, a new generation of artists emerged who considered this crisis to be a complete chaos in all spheres of life and everyday life, and were powerless to transform the truth into new positive ideals.

This generation of artists showed the chaos and confusion of the society living in those regions of Italy. That is why, in the works of many early Mannerists, the sense of conflict between them and the reality surrounding them, the loss of faith in Renaissance ideals, and the attempts to gradually isolate oneself from the real world and its contradictions are increasing more and more. This leads the mannerists to the disappearance of great positive ideas and moral values, faith in man.

In the art of the Mannerists, the human image loses not only its heroic significance, but gradually loses its content and independent meaning, subjecting itself to conventionality and a purely aristocratic ideal. Refusal of Renaissance realism, the artist's attempt to contrast the subjective fantasy world with reality leads to subjectivism characteristic of early mannerism painting, deliberate distortion of the dimensions of human figures, subjection to a free linear scheme, disharmony of color, and irrational construction of space.

The second stage of Mannerism coincides with the stabilization of the Italian feudal-Catholic movement. It began in the 1540s and lasted until the beginning of XVII century. During this time, Mannerism already went beyond the boundaries of its previous circle, became the dominant trend in court art and the entire territory of the country.

Mature Mannerist painting, while denying Renaissance trends, was also connected to the ideology of feudal-Catholic circles and served to glorify the Church and the government. The confusion and pessimism of

early Mannerism gives way to cold formality, aesthetic ideals become more lifeless, the artist's creativity as a whole is hardened by the system of dogmas and canons.

Florence was the main center where the trend of Mannerism was formed. In the 1520s, its most brilliant representative was Jacopo Carucci da Pontormo (1494-1557).

Pontormo, a talented artist who tried to find new ways for Renaissance art, appears at first as a daring innovator. Leonardo da Vinci, who was his first teacher, and Andrea del Sarto in 1512 played a big role in his formation as an artist. In his first important fresco, "The Meeting of Mary with Elizabeth" (1514-1516), Church of Santa Annunziata), Pontormo acts as a typical representative of the High Renaissance. His compositions are characterized by monumental spaciousness and solemnity, his heroes, whose clothes are wrinkled with voluminous layers, are slender, strong and beautiful. Their movements and gestures are distinguished by their perfect plastic beauty. Still, the formal-academic Florentine painting did not satisfy Pontormo, and he began to look for new ways. New aspects appear in his works.

The synthesis of these searches appears in a fresco in a Medici villa near the city of Prato (1520-1521). He chooses an unexpected motif in his painting dedicated to the myth "Vertumi and Pomona". In the evening, it shows the recreation scene of the villagers. Here he conveys the poetic unity of nature and man to the audience. All in all, the rospis is filled with the cheerful mood of the Renaissance. At the same time, in the artistic solution of the image of the barefoot old peasant sitting on the ground, one can feel concreteness, which is not characteristic of Florentine art, an attempt to approach living nature.

After some time, during the period of 1522-1525, under the influence of the northern Renaissance, he worked for the monastery in Galuccio, such as "Fate of Joseph", "Bow of the Magi", "Jesus in front of the Prophet Pilate" and others. In these frescoes, the language of description changes considerably, the lengthening of the figures typical of the Gothic style is noticeable.

In 1525, in the altar of the same monastery, in the fresco "The Prophet Jesus at Emmaus", the contrast with the earlier traditions of Renaissance painting becomes even sharper. The figures of the apostles depicted by Pontormo as ordinary people with bare rough legs, the pious simple faces of the patron monarchs standing out from the darkness of the background were so realistically resolved by the contrast of light and shade that they admired Caravaggio and became the source of inspiration for working in this manner. Tense rhythms, restless lines of silhouettes, broken wrinkles bring movement to this unreal environment.

Pontormo's fresco "The Entombment" in the church of Santa Felicita in Florence is one of the most tragic works of XVI century Italian art. Filled with deep and agonizing sadness, this work is highly emotional. The figures seem to be in the air, their feet just touching the ground. This aspect increases the unreality of the work even more.

The brokenness of religious images and Pontormo's free descriptive language are noticeable in the works "Meeting of Mary with Elizabeth" (Fig.2) and "Mary with Baby" (1521-1522), which Pontormo worked on in 1528-1530. In his works such as "Laying

into a Coffin" and "Mary with the Baby", Pontormo confirms himself as one of the founders of Mannerism. After the 1530s, being surrounded by contemporaries who did not understand him resulted in constant creative failures. In particular, his frescoes in the church of San Lorenzo, where he devoted 10 years of his life (1546-1556), were destroyed in XVIII century.

One of the founders of Florentine mannerism was Rosso Fiorentino (1495-1540). He had a number of similarities with Pontormo even early on. From 1517-1518, Rosso abandoned the ideal style, tending to be highly emotional and dramatic. If Pontormo was attracted by deep emotionality, realistic sharpness in the art of the northern renaissance, Rosso sought support for his anti-realistic, formal style.

In his first compositions, such as "Mary with Four Saints", one can find the image of strange reclusive ascetics with excessively elongated bodies and incredibly small heads. They are emphasized with expressive gestures. The color of the work is striking with the sharpness of color harmony. Deliberate deformation of human figures, distortion of faces is characteristic of Rosso's work. Lev Lyubimov said: "Rosso's depiction of saints looked like demons" [4, p. 280].

In his work "Moses and Iofar's Daughters", a tendency towards paradox is felt through the free angles of the figures. After arriving in Rome in 1517, he gave up unusualness and adapted to the requirements and tastes of the palace environment, striving for decorativeness and ornamentation in his works. After moving to France in 1530, Rosso became one of the founders of the Fontainebleau school.

In the 20s and 30s of XVI century, the humanistic and realistic crisis of the Renaissance also manifested itself in Roman art. But in Rome it takes on a unique character. The artists did not abandon the traditions of the High Renaissance, on the contrary, their creativity became more and more popular, and they became known as imitative epigones of Michelangelo and Raphael. Sebastiano del Pyombo, Perino del Vaga, Julio Romano can be mentioned among them. They reworked the formal points and nuances of the fragmented decorative systems of the monumental frescoes of their teacher (Perino del Vaga, cf. the frescoes of the Castle of Saint Angela, 1540s).

The crisis manifests itself in the most prominent works of the Palazzo del Te in Mantua, where Giulio Romano worked between 1528 and 1535. Among these frescoes, the Hall of Giants is particularly interesting. By skillfully using illusionary effects, the author combined the ceiling and the walls of the hall into a single composition. Unlike Michelangelo's fresco "The Terrible Court", the main character does not exist in this composition. All the plots here are filled with the pathos of death and destruction, which gives these images an anti-humanistic appearance characteristic of Mannerism.

The first phase of Mannerism is completed by the work of Parmian painter Francesco Macchola (1503-1540) alias Parmigianino. The influence of his teacher Correggio can be felt in his first monumental series in the church of San Giovanni Evangelista (1519/22) and in the frescoes (1523/30) of one of his rooms in the castle of Fontanellato near Parm. In the murals in Fontanellato, Parmigianino transformed the mirrored ceiling into a cloudy sky with his art.

But in the early days, he moved away from the principles of the Renaissance. This is noticeable in his self-portrait dated 1522-1524. Here, he depicted not his young appearance, but his reflection in a spherical mirror, as if breaking his appearance in a unique way. This miniature portrait, engraved on the convex part of a wooden spoon, was painted with illusory precision, with an optical effect that distorts reality.

In 1524, Parmigianino moved to Rome, where his anti-Renaissance tendencies intensified.

Parmigianino's aesthetic taste was well suited to the palatial environment. He did not like pessimism, tragic contradiction. The descriptive language of the artist in "Maryam with a rose" (1528-1530) emphasizes that the images of the virtual composition do not belong to the real world.

Parmigianino's aesthetic ideal becomes more subjective in his works of 1531-1540. The synthesis of the artist's creative searches over the years can be seen in the work "Long-necked Mary" (Fig.1). The images in the work are strange and unreal.

According to N.A. Dmitriyeva, the human figures drawn by the Mannerists were a repetition of the images worked by Michelangelo, brought to the limit of caricature, in a snake-like form [3, p. 284].

Certain canons embodying his ideal had already been formed in Parmigianino's work: people's seemingly stretched and elongated forms, unnatural, fluid lines of the silhouette subject to snake-like rhythms are of this type.

The subjectivity of Parmigianino's creative fantasy, the attempt at freedom of the descriptive language reaches its climax in the work "Long-necked Mary" and proves that Mannerism still continues.

Mannerist paintings, characterized by the play of light and shade, spots and lines, also led to the development of engravings. The development of etching and colored woodcuts, new types of engraving in XVI century Italy, is closely associated with Parmigianino's name.

In the artists of this period, in some cases, the indifference towards people and the tendency to formal experiments reached such a point that their artistic searches and works act as the first sprouts of the trends that exist in the art of XX century and in our modern time. Luca Cambiasso (1527-1585), who depicts human figures in a voluminous geometric form, and Giuseppe Archimboldo (1526-1593), who depicts people and nature in a strange allegory of various plants, fruits and vegetables, are among such artists (Fig.3).

Their creativity and innovation would stimulate the creativity of many later symbolic allegory artists of the world [7].

A brilliant representative of mature mannerism in Florence was Agnolo Bronzino (1503-1572). He was one of the creators of solemn portrait in manneristic style. We can show "Portrait of Ugolino Martelli" as an example. This genre became the leading genre in his work until the 1540s. In his subsequent portraits, Bronzino sets an invisible boundary between the viewer and

the image. Anxiety and uncertainty disappear. A living person avoids describing his feelings. Portraits of "Stefano Colonna", "Janettino Doria", "Eleonora Toledskaya" are examples of this.

One of the representatives of Florentine mannerist art was Francesco Salviati (1510-1563). Like Bronzino, he was one of the prominent portrait masters of his time. Salviati was also engaged in monumental-decorative painting. But unlike Bronzino, he never becomes a painter dependent on the palace. This free creativity of his defines the character of his portraits.

Salviati acts as Bronzino's antipode. If Bronzino tried to show the official, luxurious appearance of aristocrats, hiding the feelings and thoughts of the model under a mask of cold indifference, Salviati chose his portrait heroes from among his contemporaries, who were inwardly uncertain and full of a sense of the intractability of life's contradictions. In his "Unknown person with a letter", "Portrait of a man", "Unknown" portraits, the heroes are immersed in melancholic thoughts, and they seem to be randomly drawn on a neutral background.

Later, in the second half of XVI century, interest in the inner world of a person led to the emergence of the intimate-psychological portrait genre. But under the constant pressure of the principles of palace culture, these initiatives and innovations could not spread widely.

The decline of mature mannerism is more evident in monumental-decorative painting. This type of painting had to serve the fame of the papacy and the ruling dynasty. Artists who try to do this fill their huge compositions with a large number of figures in the most difficult and strange postures, in order to increase efficiency and impact. In such wall paintings, human figures look lifeless, indifferent and devoid of expressiveness. Templates are used in the construction of the composition and the solution of individual figures. This allows artists to decorate huge walls in a short period of time.

In the middle of XVI century, Mannerist tendencies manifest themselves in the works of Niccolo dell Abbate (1509/12-1571), Federigo Barocci (1535-1612). They try to challenge the academic structure in their paintings. In Barocchi's works "Rest on the Road to Egypt" (1573), "Madonna del Popolo" (1579), the elegance of the female characters, flirtatious mannerisms, and smiling faces surrounded by filtered light are doll-like and take on a sweet character.

Barocci's "Julio della Rovere" (1580) and his self-portrait contain a spiritualism that brings him closer to El Greco (1541-1614). Greek-born El Greco went to Venice in 1570 at the age of 26. During his stay in Italy, he enriches his individual manner with elements of mannerism.

At the end of XVI century and in early XVII century, Mannerist painting completely declines and gives way to the Baroque style, which had a great influence and was just beginning to form.

Figure 1. Parmigianino "Long-necked Mary" (1528/30), 216x132 cm, oil on wood, Uffizi Cathedral, Florence

Figure2. Jacopo Pontormo "The Meeting of Mary with Elizabeth" (1528-1529), 202x156 cm, oil on wood, Carmignano, San Michele and San Francesco church

Figure 3. Giuseppe Archimboldo "Vertumn" (1591), 70x57, 60x56cm, oil on wood, Stockholm, Skoklosters Slott

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